

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VIII, August 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

 @pinagpalapublishing

 pinagpala_publishing

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com

**UTILIZATION OF TEACHER-MADE E-GAMES AND E-TOOLS ON
IMPROVING THE MASTERY ON MULTIPLICATION TABLE OF GRADE
FOUR PUPILS IN TUNGAL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL, SCHOOL YEAR
2018-2019**

Michelle O. Pagkaliwagan, MAED

Teacher III

Tungal Elementary School

Batangas Province, Batanga, Region IV-A CALABARZO, Philippines

RESEARCH ABSTRACT

The Department of Education (DepEd) implements programs and projects aiming to assess, analyze and act on the development of the school processes focusing on the learner's needs to build a continuous learning and improvement. In relation with this, Tungal Elementary School (TES) keeps on soaring high to achieve the DepEd mission, vision and goals specifically on the pupil development.

Unfortunately, pupils' low performance in most learning areas had been alarming among the teachers and administrator. In Grade Four class, the teacher encountered many pupils who had low mastery in the different skills included in the First Grading Mathematics competencies. Grade 4 pupils in Tungal Elementary School got only 65.76 Mean Percentage in the First Periodic Test in Mathematics in the school year 2018-2019. Also, among 23 Grade Four pupils in the school year 2018-2019, 3 or 13.04 percent had mastery on multiplication table while 20 or 86.96 percent did not have mastery. The data imply that only few pupils had mastered the basic multiplication table from numbers 1 to 10.

This action research aimed to determine the level of mastery of Grade Four pupils in the school year 2018-2019, to identify the causes why the pupils could not master multiplication table; to identify the current processes involved for pupils' mastery on multiplication table; the significance of the innovative Project TIMES with the emphasis on the e-games tool utilization as innovative material for improving the pupils' mastery on multiplication table; the significant difference between the Pre and Post Assessment Results on mastering Multiplication Table after implementing the innovative project.

Significantly, this study was a great help for Mathematics teachers, class adviser and parents to understand why pupils could not master Multiplication table. This also explained the significant difference between the current and improved processes in mastering Multiplication Table and its impact for each pupil's academic improvement. Improving pupils' mastery on Multiplication Table would have significant effect in the school's academic excellence specifically in increasing the pupils' performance in the Quarterly Examinations especially in Mathematics as part of Key Result Area 2 on Pupils'/Students' Outcomes under the Result-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). Moreover, it would serve as a significant reference for future researchers to determine the effectiveness of improved processes in mastering Multiplication Table.

After the study, the researcher had the following findings:

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

(1) Out of 23 Grade Four pupils in the school year 2018-2019, only one had mastery on Multiplication Table in the 50-Item Teacher-Made Pre-Assessment while the remaining 22 pupils had no mastery.

(2) The causes why 22 Grade Four pupils in Tungal Elementary School could not master multiplication table were insufficient technology-based instructional materials and strategies, teacher's inconsistency of monitoring and evaluation and parents' inconsistent supervision at home.

(3) The current processes involved for pupils' mastery on multiplication table utilized by the researcher were reciting the multiplication table by individual, pair or group; utilizing the printed materials and evaluating pupils' mastery.

(4) To improve the mastery on multiplication table of Grade Four pupils in Tungal Elementary School, the innovative Project TIMES (Technology Integration on Multiplication for Eminence and Service) focusing on preparing and utilizing E-Games and E-Tools had a significant impact and implication in the study.

(5) After utilizing e-games and e-tools as the innovative instructional materials on implementing Project TIMES (Technology Integration on Multiplication for Eminence and Service), there is a significant difference between Teacher-Made 50-Item Pre and Post Assessment results. Using the standard formula for correlated t-test, the t-ratio for level of mastery on Multiplication Table is 8.93 which exceeds the critical t of 2.819 at the .01 level.

Moreover, the researcher made the following conclusions after the study:

(1) Out of 23 Grade Four pupils in the school year 2018-2019, 22 of them did not have mastery on Multiplication Table in the 50-Item Teacher-Made Pre-Assessment. This affected their learning of Mathematics competencies involving multiplication facts.

(2) Traditional teaching strategies and instructional materials were not suited for pupils' mastery on multiplication table. Also, teachers and parents have significant roles for pupils' learning.

(3) Teacher's current processes on pupils' mastery on multiplication table should be better replaced by the initiated innovative Project TIMES with the emphasis on the utilization of e-games and e-tools.

(4) Utilization of e-games and e-tools had a significant impact in the study as shown in an outstanding mastery level on multiplication table with the percentile score between 90 to 100 while 6 or 26 percent had a satisfactory mastery level with the percentile score between 80-84. Only 3 or 13 percent had a fairly satisfactory that ranges between 75 to 79 percentile score. The data imply that Project TIMES implementation through utilizing e-games and e-tools helped to improve the mastery level of grade four pupils with the intended and unintended benefits.

(5) The implementation of Project TIMES (Technology Integration on Multiplication for Eminence and Service) focusing on preparing and utilizing E-Games and E-Tools had a positive effect on improving the level of mastery on Multiplication Table of Grade 4 respondents, as evidenced by the significant greater mean in the Teacher-Made 50-item Post Assessment than in the Pre-Assessment.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13359388

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.